

CULTiVATE

The Mapping, Tracking and Monitoring of FSIs: Manual Mapping Protocol

WP 2

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WP2: The Mapping, Tracking and Monitoring of FSIs.

Drawing on the approach developed in SHARECITY to identify what is shared, how and through what business model, the TCD CULTIVATE team has created a multilingual list of terms that will be used to search for, and categorise, FSIs across EU Member States and Associated Countries [MS/AC]. In this collation phase, WP2 developed an expanded multilingual dictionary for comprehensively identifying the practice and performance of urban food sharing (T2.1) which will be utilised to extend the SHARECITY100 database to include 100 additional EU MS/AC cities through combining reflexive coding and online collaboration.

Deliverable 2.1 [Manual for categorising FSIs, including the European Food Sharing Dictionary] was developed by the TCD team through a multistage approach in collaboration with DCU ADAPT, other partners, professional translation services and other contributors.

Developing a list of search and categorisation terms.

Before a list of terms of searching and categorising FSIs could be compiled, WP2 leads met with DCU ADAPT partners to discuss the exploratory development of an AI functionality of the SHARECITY200 database. This was a necessary starting point to clarify the needs of the SHARECITY200 database and to ensure that the list of terms created would be appropriate for the development of an automated search and coding functionality. Following this, WP2 leads could begin compiling the list of terms.

Drawing on Prof Anna Davies experience of leading the SHARECITY team in searching for and coding FSIs, WP2 leads created a revised list of search and categorisation terms for CULTIVATE. Building from the terms used throughout SHARECITY, the refined list used by CULTIVATE is designed to be better reflective of the contemporary European food sharing landscape. In addition to removing terms that were considered unproductive, problematic or unnecessary, the plural versions of remaining terms were added where appropriate and new terms were added that would enable for both manual and automated searching and coding of FSIs.

Given the usefulness of SHARECITY's categories of FSIs in accurately presenting FSIs according to what is shared, how it is shared and through what business model it is shared, the WP2 leads considered it pertinent to utilise these categories for CULTIVATE. However, an additional category of **Public Sector** was added to capture FSIs which operate through that business model.

Ultimately a list of 158 English terms was compiled, which can be divided into 6 groups.

- 90 key search terms were chosen. These 90 terms include:
 - 36 base search terms which consist of individual words or terms of two or more words to search for specific food sharing practices and activities.
 - 13 plural versions of base search terms.
 - 41 combined search terms. These are composed from 7 of the base search terms in addition with one of 9 supplementary terms. This will ensure specific search results for the 7 generic base search terms. These 7 base search terms are: "Community Garden", "Community Gardens", "Shared Garden", "Shared Gardens", "Skill Sharing", "Sharing Skills" and "Sharing Economy".
- 14 search terms for initiatives. These are to be searched for with each of the 90 key search terms, to ensure that the search results returned are representative of FSIs rather than food sharing practices more broadly.

- 3 search terms to limit search results to those within the EU. These three terms are “Europe”, “European Union” and “EU”.
- 29 categorisation terms relate specifically to the categories for the SHARECITY200 website, including those used to categorise what is shared, how it is shared and through what business model it is shared.
- 34 categorisation terms which will be used for analysis by the CULTIVATE team to track the range of social and environmental issues that FSIs aim to address through their food sharing practices. These terms relate to 14 categories of social and environmental foci. These categories will not be presented on the SHARECITY200 database but will be used by CULTIVATE partners to better understand the myriad of social and environmental injustices that FSIs are tackling in Europe.
- 9 categorisation terms which will be used for analysis by the CULTIVATE team and which will not be presented on the SHARECITY200 database. These terms relate to 4 categories of “Growing”, “Cooking”, “Eating”, and “Redistributing” food.
- Please note that the number of terms will vary between languages as several of the English language terms have multiple relevant translations.

Search Process.

To manually search online for FSIs in a chosen UPU location, follow the below process:

1. Choose a Key Term from Column A or B of the “Terms_Master_Doc” Excel Sheet and enter it into the search bar.
 - a. For example: “Community Garden”.
2. Where relevant, choose an additional search term from Column C or D and type it into the search bar. Be sure to separate both search terms by adding “**AND**” between them.
 - a. For example: “Community Garden AND Food”.
3. Enter the chosen Key Term(s) into the search bar followed by “**AND**” and a term from Column E [Search Terms 2 – FSIs].
 - a. For example: “Community Garden AND Initiative” or “Community Garden AND Food AND Initiative”.
4. To limit search results to a specific UPU location, type “**AND**” and inset the UPU’s name.
 - a. For example: “Community Garden AND Food AND Initiative AND Paris”.
5. If the UPU location’s name has a commonly use adjective, then you can also search with this. To do this, please duplicate the above search sequence followed by “**OR**” and then the search sequence with the UPU location’s adjective in the place of the name. Search results from this will cover both the UPU location’s name and adjective.
 - a. For example: Community Garden AND Food AND Initiative AND Paris OR Community Garden AND Food AND Initiative AND Parisian.

Categorisation Process.

Once you have found an FSI, explore their web or social media page to retrieve the necessary information to categorise them in line with the SHARECITY200 Database and the additional category to document FSI’s social and environmental focus. This information will generally be available in the “About us” sections of their websites and social media accounts. The 4 categories are below:

1. **What is shared:** Please categorise the FSIs according to the food related items that they share in their activities. To do this, please select from the 11 options provided in Table 1. Please note that you can choose as many options as relevant.

Food	Knowledge
Compost	Skills
Tool	Meal

Land	Plants
Kitchen Space	Seeds
Kitchen Devices	

Table 1: What is Shared.

2. **How it is shared:** Please categorise the FSIs according to the mode of sharing that they use in their food sharing activities. If the FSI engages in multiple modes of sharing, then please categorise them as “Multifunctional”. For example, if the FSI collects food from foraging while also gifting it to communities, please categorise it as multifunctional. The 5 modes of sharing are listed below.

Collect	Sell
Gift	Multifunctional
Barter	

Table 2: How it is Shared.

3. **Sharing organisation:** Please categorise the FSI according to their business model. To do this, there are 10 categories listed in Table 3.

Charity	Club
Non-Profit	Association
Social Enterprise	Network
For-Profit	Informal Network
Cooperative	Public Sector

Table 3: Sharing Organisation.

4. **Social and environmental focus:** Using the 15 options provided in Column G of the “List of Terms” Excel Sheet, please categorise the FSIs according to their focus on social and environmental concerns.

Education	Age	Social Justice
Low Income	(Dis)Ability	Climate Change
Gender	Migrant	Sustainability
Ethnicity	Marginalised	Biodiversity
Race	Disadvantaged	Other (Please Specify)

Table 4: Social and Environmental Focus.

5. **Growing, Cooking, Eating and Redistributing of food:** Using the options provided in Column H, please categorise the FSI according to one of the 4 categories listed in Table 5 below.

Growing	Cooking
Eating	Redistributing

Documentation Process.

Each Excel spreadsheet includes 4-5 key sheets:

1. Search and Categorisation Terms: Each Excel spreadsheet will include the English terms, plus any additional relevant languages.
2. “Search_Results”: This is where all FSIs that are found using search terms must be documented.
3. “Offline_Results”: There are two types of entries to be inputted here, where relevant:

- a. Offline FSIs: This is where you can add any FSIs that you know of, or have found, that DO NOT have their own web presence (URL address, website, social media page, etc).
 - b. Online FSIs not found using Search Terms: This is also where you can add any FSIs that you know of, or have found, that DO have a web presence, but which you have NOT found using the search terms provided. If you later find these FSIs using the search terms, they can be copied and pasted to the “Search_Results” sheet, and deleted from the “Offline_Results” sheet.
4. “Rejected_Results”: Please add search results here that were not deemed to be FSIs. **PLEASE NOTE** that you do not need to add all rejected results here, **ONLY** the results that you were initially unsure of, but that you later decided to reject. It is important that we document these “close calls” so that our DCU partners can better develop the automated functionality.

Please complete the Excel spreadsheet as appropriate by following the below Process:

1. Column A: Please insert the country.
2. Column B: Please insert the UPU location.
3. Column C: Please insert the name of the FSI.
4. Column D to Column I: Please insert the URL for the FSI’s website, Meetup, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, or App as appropriate.
5. Column J: Please insert short a description of the FSI’s focus and activities.
6. Column K: Using the SHARECITY200 categories in Table 1 above, please insert what is shared from the relevant 11 options. Please note that you can choose as many options as relevant.
7. Column L: Using the SHARECITY200 categories in Table 2 above, please insert how it is shared from the relevant 5 options.
8. Column M: Using the SHARECITY200 categories in Table 3 above, please insert the type of Sharing Organisation as appropriate for its business model from the relevant 10 options.
9. Column N: Using the options in Table 4, please categorise the social and environmental focus of the FSI’s from the 14 options listed. If the relevant focus is not listed, please insert the alternative appropriate social and environmental focus. Please note that you can select more than one category where appropriate.
10. Column O: Using the Option in Table 5, please categorise the FSIs according to their focus on growing, cooking, eating, or redistributing food. Multiple options can be selected where relevant.
11. Column P: If you have any additional comments regarding the FSI, please insert them here.
12. Column Q: Insert the address of the FSI if known.
13. Column R: Please insert the date that you searched for the FSI here.
14. Column S: Please copy and paste the search query used to find the FSI here. For example: Supper Club AND Network AND Milan.
15. Column T: Merge cells here to indicate if the FSIs were found using the above search process, or another method. For example, using terms from an additional language, an alternative term for geographical location, or if they were found through the mapping of offline FSIs.

Google My Maps:

When adding FSIs to the Excel spreadsheet, please add them to a Google My Maps simultaneously. Doing this will create a helpful visual tool to aid with analysis of food sharing landscapes. To do this, please follow the below process:

1. Go to “Google My Maps”.

2. Once logged in, select the “+Create A New Map” tab.

3. On the new map, select “Untitled map” and rename it as “[Insert City Name] Manual Map”. For example, “Barcelona Manual Map”. You can also add a description of the map.

4. Select “Base map” at the bottom of the legend. Select “Light Political” as the base map. This will allow for a clearer end map with less unwanted markers.

5. Next, you will create your layers. To do this, first select "Untitled layer" and rename it as "Growing".

6. Then select "Add layer". This will create an additional layer. Rename this layer "Cooking". To rename these additional layers, select the three dots icon to the right of the highlighted "Untitled layer" (images above). Repeat this process 3 more times, calling the layers "Eating", "Redistributing" and "Multifunctional". This will give you a total of 5 layers.

7. To add an FSI to the map, first select on the layer that you are adding the FSI to. This layer should reflect your coding from the Excel spreadsheet. For example, if you have coded the FSI as "growing" in Column O of your spreadsheet, then you should add the FSI to the

“Growing” layer here. If you add an FSI to the wrong layer, then you can drag it into the correct layer.

8. Next, enter the address of the FSI into the search bar from Column Q of your Excel spreadsheet. Select the correct option. A pin will drop onto the map. Once you are certain that it is the correct location, click on the pin and select “+ Add to map”.

9. This FSI has now been added to your map under “Growing”.

10. You now need to edit the pin icon and colour. To edit these, select the pin on the map. Select the colour tab and choose the colour. Then select the “More icons” option and search for the icon using the filter search bar. Once you have chosen an icon, it will appear as a

recently used icon and won't need to be searched for again. For each layer, we have a common icon and colour as seen below.

- Growing: Dark Green colour [code: RGB (9, 113, 56)]. Icon is the “health food” icon.
- Cooking: Dark Yellow colour [code: RGB (255, 214, 0)]. Icon is the “grill” icon.
- Eating: Blue colour [code: RGB (2, 136, 209)]. Icon is “restaurant” icon.
- Redistribution: Deep Red colour [code: RGB (194, 24, 91)]. Icon is the “Shopping Basket” icon.
- Multifunctional: Purple colour [code: RGB (156, 39, 176)]. Icon is the “star” icon.

- Next, download the shapefiles for your chosen country from the [OECD Functional Urban Areas](#). Extract your chosen urban area's files, both the “core hub” area and the “commuting are hub”. Export these files as KMZ. On your Google My Map, Select “Add layer” as before. Under the new layer, select “Import” and upload your KMZ file. This will add two new layers to your map representing the “core urban area” and “commuting zone” as defined by the OECD.

12. Lastly, be sure to share your map with Anna Davies and any other relevant WP2 partners by selecting the “+Share” tab, followed by “Anyone with this link can view”. Copy the link and share access.

Uncertainties

If you are unsure about the most accurate categorisation for a FSI, please raise your concerns at the coding workshops or at your check-ins with Dean and Anna.